

**COMPARATIVE STUDIES ON THE EFFECTS OF ATROPINE, VITAMIN C AND
DATURA SEED EXTRACTS ON PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS USING MALE
ECO-TYPE CHICKENS**

BY

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**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
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AUGUST, 2024.

DECLARATION

I, **FAGB ULE TAIWO SOLOMON**, hereby declare that this report was written by me and it is a record of all activities carried out during the coursework and research for the award of Bachelor of Agriculture in Animal Production and Health. All sources of information are clearly acknowledged by means of references. The work embodied in this report is original and has not been submitted in part or full for any other diploma or degree or this or any other university.

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FAGB ULE TAIWO SOLOMON

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Date

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this research was carried out under supervision by **FAGBULE TAIWO SOLOMON**, with matriculation number **APH/18/035** and submitted to the Department of Animal Production and Health, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa, Ondo State, Nigeria.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this report to Almighty God for his unlimited grace, consistent love and immeasurable faithfulness for sparing my life, throughout the period of my research.

Secondly, to my incomparable parents Late Mr. Koyejo Fagbule (of blessed memories) and Mrs. Kehinde Fagbule, as well as my lovely siblings and big uncles that have supported me to this level for their moral, encouragement, financial and spiritual support over these years. May you eat the fruit of your labor in Jesus name.

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to compare the physiological parameters of 12 male eco-type chicken, in which the treatment was divided into four groups: a control group, an Atropine-treated group, a Datura seed extract-treated group and Vitamin C (ascorbic acid)-treated group. The study lasted for three weeks with each bird group having 3 Matured cock respectfully using Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The first two weeks being the acclimation period for the birds to settle in the experimental plot with food and water given to the birds at *ad libitum* because of other materials to be tested. The transportation protocol involved a journey designed to simulate typical commercial transport conditions, including confinement, handling, and movement stressors. The physiological parameters assessed was Rectal Temperature (RT), Respiratory Rate (RR), Pulse Rate (PR) and Heart Rate (HR) were measured.

The result indicated that tested ingredient influenced the physiological parameters ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, it can be concluded from this study that the Datura plant extract, Vitamin C and Atropine can alleviate stress and improve animal management practices.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The role of the Poultry industry in producing animal protein effectively within the shortest possible time cannot be overemphasized due to the rapid growth and prolificacy (Hosseinzadeh *et al.*, 2010). Some of the problems limiting poultry production in Nigeria are diseases, high cost of feed, heat stress and poor reproductive rate (low fertility and hatchability) and this is majorly due to the usage of exotic chicken that evolved to suit the climatic regions of the temperate. The broiler chicken is a rapid growing meat-type chicken with high feed conversion ratio but associated with high level of heat stress, high susceptibility to diseases and remains very fragile compared to the Nigerian Indigenous chicken (Salako *et al.*, 2006). Some physiological parameters that can be used to determine positive or negative physiological response of animals (chicken) includes haematology and serum biochemistry, heart rate, respiratory rate, rectal temperature amongst others (Salako *et al.*, 2006). Rectal temperature (RT), Heart rate (HR) and Panting Rate (PR) are part of physiological responses that reflect thermoregulation and the health status of animals, these parameters has been suggested as indicators of the level of heat stress in chickens (Deeb, N *et al.*, 1999). The potentials of the Nigerian Indigenous chicken (NIC) most especially the Fulani Eco-type chicken which was noted by (Olori. V. E. 1992) as an heavy ecotype chicken found in the dry Savannahs (Guinea and Sahel Savannah), Montane regions and cattle Kraals of the North which are known to be hotter than most regions in Nigeria and weigh about 0.9-2.5 kg at maturity have not been fully harnessed.

Local chickens are important in overall food production systems in developing economies mostly because of their adaptation to the tropical environment. They may appear to produce less than highly specialized commercial breeds; however, they possess attributes that make their sustainability on available local resources more ecological and economical in the long term (Oleforuh-Okoleh, V. U. 2013, Mkpugbe, J. I. *et al.*, 2015). Incorporation of the Nigerian local chicken as a parent breed stock in the nation's breeding programme is important to meet the increase in poultry product demand by the citizenry.

Atropine is a naturally occurring tropane alkaloid extracted in several plants of the Solanaceae including *Atropa belladonna*, *Datura inoxia*, *Datura metel*, *Datura stramonium*, *Brugmansia spp.* and *Hyoscyamus spp.* Plants such as *Datura metel*, *Datura stramonium* naturally occur in tropical West Africa. Atropine is a tropane alkaloid extracted from the deadly nightshade (*Atropa*

belladonna) and other plants of the family Solanaceae. It is a secondary metabolite of these plants and serves as a drug with a wide variety of effects. It is a competitive antagonist for the muscarinic acetylcholine receptor. Atropine is found in many members of the Solanaceae family. The most commonly found sources are *Atropa belladonna*, *Datura innoxia*, *D. metel*, and *D. stramonium*. Other sources include members of the Brugmansia and Hyoscyamus genera. Atropine is a competitive antagonist for the muscarinic acetylcholine receptor types and it is classified as an anticholinergic drug (parasympatholytic). Working as a nonselective muscarinic acetylcholinergic antagonist, atropine increases firing of the sinoatrial node (SA) and conduction through the atrioventricular node (AV) of the heart, opposes the actions of the vagus nerve, blocks acetylcholine receptor sites, and decreases bronchial secretions. Topical atropine is used as a cycloplegic, to temporarily paralyze the accommodation reflex. As a mydriatic, to dilate the pupils. glaucoma (eye disease), bradycardia, asthma and COPD, gastrointestinal disorders, poisoning and parkinson's disease. General effects of atropine include dry mouth, blurred vision, dilated pupils, increased heart rate, urinary retention, confusion or delirium, constipation, flushing or dry skin, difficulty in swallowing, dizziness, fatigue, restlessness, reduced Secretions from glands and relaxation of smooth muscles.

Datura is a genus of nine species of highly poisonous, vespertine-flowering plants belonging to the nightshade family (Solanaceae). They are commonly known as thornapples or jimson weeds, but are also known as devil's trumpets (not to be confused with angel's trumpets, which are placed in the closely related genus Brugmansia). Other English common names include moonflower, devil's weed, and hell's bells. All species of *Datura* are extremely poisonous and psychoactive, especially their seeds and flowers, which can cause respiratory depression, arrhythmias, fever, delirium, hallucinations, anticholinergic syndrome, psychosis, and death if taken internally. Traditionally it is used in skin disorders, ear pain, cough, fever and asthma. Juice of fruit is used for body pain, leaves are externally used for injuries, wounds, bleeding and pains and juice of fruit is applied to the scalp for falling hair and as antidandruff.

Datura stramonium contains biologically active substances like alkaloids, atropine, scopolamine, tannin, carbohydrates and proteins. It is used in many drugs due to its analgesic and antiasthmatic activities. The effects of *Datura* consumption can be highly variable and unpredictable. They may include hallucinations, delirium, tachycardia, dry mouth, blurred vision, urinary retention, and even potentially dangerous outcomes such as respiratory depression or coma. Both atropine and

Datura extracts exert their effects primarily through the antagonism of acetylcholine receptors, particularly muscarinic receptors. However, while atropine is used in controlled medical settings for its therapeutic properties, Datura extracts are potent and unpredictable due to their variable alkaloid content, making them potentially dangerous when consumed recreationally or without proper medical supervision. Eco-type chickens are often adapted to local environmental conditions and may exhibit unique physiological characteristics compared to commercial broiler or layer breeds. Overall, the objective of this study is to expand the scientific understanding of the interactions between these plant-derived compounds and the physiological responses of male eco-type chickens, which can contribute to the broader knowledge of avian pharmacology and toxicology.

Ascorbic acid, widely known as vitamin C, is an essential nutrient for animals such as poultry. Ascorbic acid in poultry feed improves animal health and thus increases the growth performance of birds. Ascorbic acid can be used in the form of synthetic products or can be naturally obtained from fruits and plants. It is soluble in water and can be easily administered in drinking water and the diet. Poultry can synthesize ascorbic acid in the body. However, the performance of the animals can be improved by adding ascorbic acid to their diet. In addition, ascorbic acid is called an antioxidant and an anti-inflammatory. This increases their resistance to disease during the transition season. Ascorbic acid supplementation positively affects the stress response, especially during the dry season in tropical countries.

Furthermore, supplementing ascorbic acid in the poultry's diet improves resistance to diseases, regulates stress, and helps in the body's oxidation process. Vitamin C is an antioxidant, along with vitamin E, beta-carotene, and many other plant-based nutrients. Antioxidants block some of the damage caused by free radicals, substances that damage DNA. The buildup of free radicals over time may contribute to the aging process and the development of health conditions such as cancer, heart disease, and arthritis.

1.1 OBJECTIVES

This research was carried out with the following objectives;

- i. To determine the effect of Atropine sulphate and Datura seed extract on the male ecotype chicken subjected to transportation stress.
- ii. To determine the effect of Atropine sulphate and Datura seed extract on physiological parameters of male ecotype chicken subjected to transportation stress.
- iii. To determine the effect of Atropine sulphate, Vitamin C and Datura seed extract on physiological parameters of male ecotype chicken subjected to transportation stress.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Poultry, particularly chickens are the most widely kept livestock species in the world and also the most numerous in Africa. Indigenous chicken in Africa are in general hardy, adaptive to rural environment, survive on little or no input and adjust to fluctuations in feed availability. Chicken largely dominate flock composition and make up about 98% of the total poultry members (chickens, ducks and turkeys) kept in Africa.

The rearing of indigenous chickens is an integral part of the smallholder farming systems in developing countries, where they are kept by the rural poor to satisfy multiple functions. Indigenous chickens are specially adapted to environmental stresses and poor husbandry practices under low-input systems, and this has made these stocks a suitable choice for smallholder production systems (Gondwe, *et al.*, 2001; Sonaiya *et al.*, 2004).

Nigeria is endowed with locally adapted chickens found in different agro-ecological zones where they contribute significantly to the livelihoods of the people who raise them in the urban, peri-urban and rural settlements. Some popular locally adapted chickens in Nigeria include the Fulani ecotype, Yoruba ecotype, and other ecotypes from the southeastern states of Nigeria (Olori, 1992; Fayeye *et al.*, 2005; Ajayi, 2010). The Fulani ecotype chicken has been described as a potential meat type breed of chickens in Nigeria because of the broiler-type body conformation, with mature body weight ranging between 0.9 Kg to 1.5 Kg and 1.5 Kg to 2.5 Kg for hens and cocks respectively (Olawunmi *et al.*, 2008; Sola-Ojo *et al.*, 2009; Jesuyon *et al.*, 2013).

2.1 DISTRIBUTION

The potentials of the Nigerian Indigenous chicken (NIC) most especially the Fulani Eco-type chicken which was noted by (Olori V. E., 1992) as an heavy ecotype chicken found in the dry Savannahs (Guinea and Sahel Savannah), Montane regions and cattle Kraals of the North which are known to be hotter than most regions in Nigeria and weigh about 0.9-2.5 kg at maturity have not been fully harnessed. The Fulani ecotype chicken has long been associated and preserved by the Fulani tribe of Northern Nigeria, who raise these chickens in Kraals (Fulani settlements) and villages under extensive or semi-intensive production systems where the Fulani chicken serves as a veritable source of proteins in term of eggs and meat, and as a means of livelihoods. The Fulani ecotype chicken is widespread across Nigeria, being taken along to different ecological zones by Fulani pastoral nomads. Though this chicken is smaller in size, with adult body weight of 0.9 Kg to 1.5 Kg and 1.5 to 2.5 Kg for hens and cocks respectively (Sola-Ojo *et al.*, 2009; Ajayi, 2010), the small body size is said to be important to reduce maintenance and feed requirements (Olawunmi, *et al.*,

2008). This is necessary for survival under the free-range system because of scarce feed resources and the uncertainty surrounding feed supply all year round (Ige, 2013).

2.2 SYSTEMS OF POULTRY MANAGEMENT

There are three systems of poultry management. The system of management defines the extents to which birds are exposed to sunshine, pasture and housing pattern. These aid:

Extensive management

Semi-intensive management

Intensive systems

Extensive Management

Under this system, the domestic fowls are allowed to roan about in search of food and water. There are no proper housing, care and feeding for these birds. Unlimited grassland is available to the birds. The capital investment is small birds. The capital investment is small and the birds population per hectare of land is minimal and production is usually very low. Example of the extensive system of rearing poultry is the free range system.

Semi-Intensive Management

The Semi-Intensive System s mid-way between intensive and extensive system. The birds are housed in a foxed building but are allowed to move about within a fenced area during the day. Their buildings are made up of wood and are raised above the ground with wire netting on the floor to permit easy dropping of faeces. A good example of the Semi-Intensive System is the fold unit system.

Intensive System

Under this system, the birds are confined within the building and the not allowed to move out. It prevents the birds from having access to pasture and sunshine. There is high stocking density which implies a closer contact among the birds. Feeds, water and all medications are provided for the birds.

Two examples of the intensive system of poultry management are:

1. Deep litter system

2. Battery cage system

2.3 DOMESTICATION AND ECONOMIC PRODUCTION OF POULTRY

Chicken domestication likely occurred more than once in southeast Asia and possibly India over the most recent 7,400 years, and the first domestications may have been for religious reasons or for the raising of fighting birds. Descendants of those domestications have spread throughout the world in several waves for at least the last 2,000 years. For most of that period, chickens were a common part of the livestock complement of farms and ranches throughout Eurasia and Africa. Only in the early 20th century, however, did chicken meat and eggs become mass-production commodities. Modern high-volume poultry farms, with rows of cages stacked indoors for control of heat, light, and humidity, began to proliferate in Great Britain about 1920 and in the United States after World Wars I and II. Females (mature hens and younger chickens, called pullets) are raised for meat and for their edible eggs. Farmers have developed numerous breeds and varieties to fulfill commercial requirements. Originally, meat production was byproduct of egg production. Only hens that could no longer produce enough eggs were killed and sold for meat. By the mid-20th century, however, meat production had outstripped egg production as a specialized industry. The market for chicken meat has grown dramatically since then, with worldwide exports reaching nearly 12.5 million metric tons (about 13.8 million tons) by the early 21st century.

Mature males have long been used for sport (i.e., cockfighting now outlawed in many jurisdictions) as well as for breeding.

Many immature males (cockerels) are castrated (usually chemically, with hormones that cause atrophy of the testicles) to become meat birds (capons).

2.3.1 MALE ECO-TYPE CHICKEN AS FOOD

Male eco-type chickens, also known as indigenous or local breed chickens, represent an important genetic resource in poultry production, particularly in regions where traditional poultry farming practices are prevalent. These chickens are adapted to local environmental conditions, exhibit robustness, and often possess desirable traits such as disease resistance, natural foraging behavior, and meat quality characteristics that are well-suited to local consumer preferences.

Local chickens are important in overall food production systems in developing economies mostly

because of their adaptation to the tropical environment. They may appear to produce less than highly specialized commercial breeds; however, they possess attributes that make their sustainability on available local resources more ecological and economical in the long term (Oleforuh-Okoleh, V. U., 2013, Mkpugbe, J. I. *et al.*, 2015). Incorporation of the Nigerian local chicken as a parent breed stock in the nation's breeding programme is important to meet the increase in poultry product demand by the citizenry.

2.3.2 MALE ECO-TYPE CHICKEN AS SUBJECT FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Using male eco-type chickens as an experimental model offers several advantages as genetic relevance: Male eco-type chickens represent a genetically diverse population, reflecting the genetic variability present in local chicken populations. There is increasing ethical considerations and emphasis on animal welfare research, using indigenous chickens as experimental models aligns with principles of reducing the use of laboratory respecting cultural values associated traditional livestock breeds. Research findings derived from male eco-type chickens are directly applicable to small-scale and backyard poultry farming systems, which are prevalent in many developing countries. Understanding how plant extract affects plant physiological parameters in these chickens can inform sustainable and culturally appropriate interventions for local poultry farmers.

2.4 GAPS IN THE LITERATURE AND HOW THE CURRENT STUDY OF DATURA AND ATROPINE ADDRESSES THESE GAPS

Based on the information available, there are several gaps in the literature regarding the comparative study of Atropine and Datura extracts on physiological parameters using male eco-type chickens.

Firstly, while there have been studies on the pharmacological effects of Datura extracts, there is a lack of research on the specific effects of Atropine and Datura extracts on physiological parameters in male eco-type chickens. This study aims to address this gap by conducting a comparative analysis of the effects of Atropine and Datura extracts on various physiological parameters in male eco-type chickens.

Secondly, there is limited information on the potential risks and toxicity associated with the use of Datura extracts and atropine in male eco-type chickens. This study will investigate the

toxicological aspects of *Datura* extracts and Atropine in male eco-type chickens, providing valuable insights into the potential risks and safety concerns associated with their use.

Lastly, there is a need for more comprehensive research on the phytochemical composition of *Datura* extracts and Atropine, particularly in the context of their effects on male eco-type chickens. This study will contribute to the literature by providing a detailed analysis of the phytochemical composition of *Datura* extracts and Atropine and their effects on various physiological parameters in male eco-type chickens.

In summary, this study aims to address the gaps in the literature by conducting a comparative analysis of the effects of Atropine, Vitamin C and *Datura* extracts on various physiological parameters in male eco-type chickens, investigating the toxicological aspects of *Datura* extracts, Vitamin C and Atropine in male eco-type chickens, and providing a detailed analysis of the phytochemical composition of *Datura* extracts and Atropine.

2.5 ETHNOBOTANICAL DESCRIPTION OF DATURA

The genus *Datura* is generally represented as annual or perennial herbs with glandular or more often simple hair (Ibrahim, M. *et al.*, 2018). Leaves of the plant are petiolate, having a simple leaf blade, and sinuate or completely dentate. They are approximately 10-20 cm in length and 5-18 cm in breadth, coated with soft and short greyish hairs (Alabri, T. H. A. *et al.*, 2014). The solitary flowers are found in inflorescences situated in leaf axils or branch forks. The larger flowers are generally actinomorphic with stout pedicels. The bracts, peduncles, and bracteoles are generally absent (Ibrahim, M. *et al.*, 2018).

Further, the funnel-shaped and elongated corolla has cuspidate lobes. In many instances, elongated anthers are observed that are longitudinally dehiscent. The unevenly dehiscent, four valved fruit is discovered as a dry capsule that is unarmed and delimited usually by remnants of the persistent calyx (Ibrahim, M. *et al.*, 2018). The plants also consist of numerous seeds compressed laterally with a curved embryo and 12 pairs of chromosomes usually. Several species of *Datura* originated at different places globally. *D. stramonium* is an annual plant with an herbaceous base that is branched and glabrous, extending up to an approximate level of 1 m (Soni, P. *et al.*, 2012). The branches are leafy, firm, erect, with pale yellow or green color, generally branched in a forked fashion. The top surface is greyish-green and dark, typically soft, while the lower surface is paler and minutely wrinkled when dehydrated. The calyx is very long, tubular,

and swollen. The seeds are dark, flat, and kidney-shaped. Fruits are comparable to walnuts and filled with thorns (hence called "thorn apple") (Soni, P. *et al.*, 2012).

2.5.1 BIOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF DATURA

Datura, in general, constitutes significant amounts of carbohydrates, fats, protein, moisture, ash content, and crude fiber. Besides, major phytochemicals found in *Datura* include alkaloids, phenolic compounds, tannins, flavonoids, and cardiac glycosides (Bagewadi, Z.K. *et al.*, 2019, Fatima, H. *et al.*, 2015). In addition, many amino acids such as alanine, phenylalanine, glutamate, and tyrosine have also been isolated from the seeds (Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017). *Datura* species are particularly rich in tropane alkaloids. Hyoscine [(--Scopolamine)] constitutes the major tropane alkaloid, along with hyoscyamine and atropine, having different concentration levels in different plant parts (Fig 1) (Jakabová, S. *et al.*, 2012, Nayyar, M.S. *et al.*, 2020). The atropine content in the leaves in *Datura metel* was found to be 0.426%, whereas hyoscyamine levels were found to be 0.426% in the seeds and 0.43% in flower (Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017). The alkaloid contents of scopolamine and atropine in the entire plant in *D. metel* increase gradually with the development of various growth stages and becomes most apparent when the plant reaches the end of its reproductive stage (Lim, K.M.C. *et al.*, 2020, Nandakumar, A. *et al.*, 2017). However, in the case of *D. stramonium*, the maximum amounts of alkaloids were found after ten weeks of seed germination, decreasing gradually with the beginning of the generative phase in plants (Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017, Al-Snafi, A.E., 2021). Generally, the alkaloid concentration varies with the plant part and different growth stages in the plant. For example, leaves develop maximum alkaloid concentration in the vegetative phase, decreasing rapidly in the generative phase (Alinejad, S. *et al.*, 2020, Oseni, O.A. *et al.*, 2010). The stems and leaves of young plants contain hyoscyamine as a significant component. However, the concentrations of atropine and scopolamine differ in different plant parts in young and adult plants.

Fig 1: Identified important phytochemicals in *Datura*, as well as their chemical structures
 (Butnariu, M., 2012)

2.5.2 PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF DATURA

Datura is known to exhibit analgesic, antioxidant, anticancer, and antimicrobial properties. Especially, owing to the potent analgesic activities, *D. metel* acts as an effective painkiller. *D. stramonium* has antifungal activity against *Fusarium mangiferae* and *Fusarium oxysporum*, alkaloids found in *D. stramonium* are potential anticholinergic agents (Maheshwari, N.O. *et al.*, 2013). Atropine and scopolamine are muscarinic antagonists that may be utilized to cure Parkinson's disease and parasympathetic stimulation of the eye, respiratory, urinary, heart, and gastrointestinal tract (Roy, S. *et al.*, 2018). They prevent parasympathetic nerve impulses by selectively blocking the binding site of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine to the receptor of nerve cells (Roy, S. *et al.*, 2016). In addition, Datura has long been utilized as a beneficial therapy for asthma symptoms. Atropine is the active anti-asthmatic agent that triggers paralysis of pulmonary branches of the lungs, removing the spasms responsible for the asthma attacks (Hameed Baloch, I.A. *et al.*, 2017).

The technique of smoking Datura leaves through a pipe to alleviate allergies has its origins in the standard ayurvedic medicine in India. *D. stramonium* is utilized recreationally mainly for its anticholinergic consequences and can be produced by boiling the crushed seeds (Soni, P. *et al.*, 2012). However, exposure of the fetus to *D. stramonium* causes a continuous release of acetylcholine, leading to desensitization of nicotinic receptors, resulting in permanent damage to the fetus (Gaire, B.P. *et al.*, 2013).

Anti-Inflammatory and Analgesic Activities

The phytochemicals present in Datura species are well-known for their anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties due to their ability to suppress the production of chemical mediators responsible for the stimulation of nociceptors and induction of pain or inflammation (Agarwal, R. *et al.*, 2019, Chandan, G. *et al.*, 2021).

The ethanolic extract of roots of *D. fastuosa* was found to exhibit anti-inflammatory activity when studied for paw edema induced by carrageenan in rats, with Indomethacin as a standard drug [137,38]. The progress of edema can be explained in different phases; release of histamine and serotonin in the initial phase, edema maintained by substances like kinin in the plateau phase, and prostaglandin release in the edema accelerating phase (Muthusamy, P. *et al.*, 2010, Nivedhitha, S.

et al., 2010). The root extracts showed considerable activity against inflammation at 200 mg/kg compared to Indomethacin (at 10 mg/kg). Moreover, the aqueous extracts of seeds and leaves possessed significant analgesic effects at 800 and 400 mg/kg dosage, respectively, when experimented on mice using a writhing test (induced by acetic acid) and hot plate reaction (Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017). However, the analgesic activity induced by leaves could be potentially decreased by naloxone, while that of seed extract remained unaffected. The aqueous leaf extracts of *D. innoxia* have been evaluated for their anti-inflammatory activity to develop an active herbal pain-relieving drug (Jaafar, F.R. *et al.*, 2018). The basic mechanism involved in anti-inflammatory and analgesic action is believed to be the cyclooxygenase (COX1 and COX2) inhibition, followed by suppression of prostaglandin-synthesis or probably the narcotic effects of *Datura* species (Chandan, G. *et al.*, 2021, Jaafar, F.R. *et al.*, 2018).

Anti-oxidation Activities

The antioxidant activity of *Datura* extracts can also be attributed to the presence of phytochemical compounds, which act as potent free radical scavengers and help prevent cellular damage (Belayneh, Y.M. *et al.*, 2019). Analysis of *Datura* plant extracts for antioxidant characteristics revealed its ability to cure various health disorders, including cancers, since antioxidants are known to inhibit cell damage, the general pathway for cancers, aging, and several other diseases (Iqbal, S. *et al.*, 2017). The antioxidant capacity of leaf extracts in different solvents, estimated by various in vitro methods, including hydroxyl radical scavenging activity, DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) scavenging activity, superoxide radical scavenging activity, β -carotene bleaching activity, and reducing power assay, revealed that chloroform extract of leaves possessed maximum concentration-dependent antioxidant activity (Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017, Khan, W. *et al.*, 2019). The IC₅₀ value of methanolic and hydroalcoholic seed extracts of *D. metel* recorded using the DPPH model showed that hydroalcoholic extract possesses slightly higher antioxidant activities (IC₅₀ of 25.78 g/mL) than methanolic seed extract (IC₅₀ of 28.34 μ g/mL) (Alam, W. *et al.*, 2020, Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017)

In the estimation of DPPH free radicals scavenging activities, a positive correlation was observed between the flavonoid and phenolic content of the *D. metel* extracts (Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017, Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017). Maximum DPPH scavenging activity of methanolic seed extracts of *D. stramonium* was found to be 59.50% at a concentration of 60 μ g/mL with IC₅₀ value of 94.87

ug/mL; similarly, the maximum superoxide radical scavenging activity was 53.17% at a concentration of 60 ug/mL, while maximum scavenging activity of hydroxyl radical was 57.88% at concentration of 30ug/mL with IC50 value of 39.59 4g/mL (Iqbal, S. *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, the hydromethanolic root extract of *D. stramonium* exhibited a significant amount of correlation with DPPH free radical scavenging activity.

Anti-Asthmatic and Bronchodilating Effects

Alkaloids found in *D. stramonium*, such as atropine and scopolamine, which possess significant anticholinergic and bronchodilating activities, block the muscarinic receptors (which are important for airways regulation), subsequently dilating bronchial smooth muscles (Choudhary, M. *et al.*, 2021, Kuraki, T., 2017). Acetylcholine (the neurotransmitter synthesized and released by cholinergic neurons) leads to the contraction of smooth muscle after interaction with cholinergic muscarinic Acetylcholine (Ach) receptors (Yamada, M. *et al.*, 2018). The muscarinic receptors associated with the airway and lung tissues are M1, M2, and M3, of which M1 and M3, fully active in asthmatics, are responsible for bronchoconstriction while M2 which suppresses the release of acetylcholine, are less functional in asthmatics (Papi, A. *et al.*, 2021). *Datura* administration inhibits M2 function, ultimately leading to the continued release of neurotransmitters. The anticholinergic activity of *D. stramonium* involves blocking the functions of muscarinic receptors on airway smooth muscles and submucosal gland cells (Kadam, S.D. *et al.*, 2018). The anti-asthmatic *D. stramonium* cigarette acts as a potential bronchodilator in asthmatic patients with the mild airway. A substantial decrease in the specific airway resistance (sRaw) was observed after inhaling smoke from the cigarette (Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017, Miraj, S., 2016). However, when exposed to the fetus during its use by the mother for asthma, *D. stramonium* releases acetylcholine. It desensitizes nicotinic receptors, resulting in slow or no response to repetitive agonist modulatory effects on the brain's functioning, consequently damaging the fetus (Gaire, B.P. *et al.*, 2013, Soni, P. *et al.*, 2012).

Anticholinergic Activity

The alkaloids found in *D. stramonium*, are organic esters used clinically as anticholinergic agents. Jimson weed has been reported as a drug of abuse and has been involved in the accidental

poisoning of humans and animals. Symptoms of acute jimson weed poisoning included dryness of the mouth and extreme thirst, dryness of the skin, pupil dilation and impaired vision, urinary retention, rapid heartbeat, confusion, restlessness, hallucinations, and loss of consciousness. The anticholinergic syndrome results from the inhibition of central and peripheral muscarinic neurotransmission (Taha S.A. *et al.*, 2012, Diker D. *et al.*, 2007, Boumba A. *et al.*, 2005).

Acaricidal, Repellent and Oviposition Deterrent Properties

The ethanol extracts obtained from both leaf and seed in *D. stramonium* (Solanaceae) were investigated for acaricidal, repellent and oviposition deterrent properties against adult two-spotted spider mites (*T. urticae* Koch) (Acari: Tetranychidae) under laboratory conditions. Leaf and seed extracts, which were applied in 167.25 and 145.75 g/ L concentrations, respectively (using a Petri leaf disc-spray tower method), caused 98% and 25% mortality among spider mite adults after 48 h. These results suggest that *D. stramonium* extracts could be used to manage the two-spotted spider mite (Kurnal N.A. *et al.*, 2019).

Antimicrobial Activity

The methanol extracts of *D. stramonium* and *Datura innoxia* showed activity against Gram positive bacteria in a dose dependent manner. Little or no antimicrobial activity was found against *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Takhi D. *et al.*, 2011). The anti-microbial activity of combined crude ethanolic extract of *D. stramonium*, *Terminalia arjuna* and *Withania somnifera* in cup plate diffusion method for antibacterial and antifungal activity. The extracts were subjected to screening to detect potential antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Micrococcus luteus* and *Candida albicans* with compare Ciprofloxacin standard drug (Sharma M.C. *et al.*, 2010).

Anticancer Activity

An integrated approach is needed to manage cancer using the growing body of knowledge gained through scientific developments. Thousands of herbal and traditional compounds are being screened worldwide to validate their use as anti-cancerous drugs. *D. stramonium* in therapeutic dose of 0.05-0.10 g was used to cure cancer. Likely unsafe produce vomiting, hypertension, loss

of consciousness may lead to coma but may interact with anti-cholinergic drugs (Balachandran P. *et al.*, 2005).

Larvicidal and Mosquito Repellent Activities

Ethanollic extracts of leaves of *D. stromonium* were evaluated for larvicidal and mosquito repellent activities against *Aedes aegypti*, *Anopheles stephensi* and *Culex quinquefasciatus*. The LDs values for larvicidal activity were found to be 86.25, 16.07 and 6.25 mg/L against *Aedes aegypti*, *Anopheles stephensi* and *Culex quinquefasciatus* respectively. The ethanolic leaves extract of *D. stromonium* provided complete protection time (mosquito repellency) of 2.7, 71.7 and 117.7 min against *Aedes aegypti*, *Anopheles stephensi* and *Culex quinquefasciatus* at higher concentration (1%) (Swathi S. *et al.*, 2012).

Pesticide Toxicity

Extract of *D. stromonium* was effective in countering the toxicity of the cypermethin pesticide toxicity (Das B.K. *et al.*, 2003).

Antifungal Activity

Antifungal activity of a concoction brewed from *D. stromonium*, *Calotropis gigantea*, *A. indica* (neem) and cow manure (T1) followed by methanol-water (70/30 v/v) extracts of *D. stromonium*, *Calotropis gigantea* and *A. indica* T2 against *Fusarium mangiferae*. The study proved that the concoction-brewed compost T1 is effective, inexpensive, easy to prepare and constitutes a sustainable and eco-friendly approach to control floral malformation in mango when it is sprayed at bud break stage and again at fruit set stage (Usha K. *et al.*, 2009).

Vibriocidal Activity

A simple in vitro screening assay was employed for the standard strain of *Vibrio cholerae*, 12 isolates of *Vibrio cholerae* non-01, and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*. Aqueous and organic solvent extracts of different parts of the plants were investigated by using the disk diffusion method. Extracts from 16 medicinal plants were selected on account of the reported traditional uses for the treatment of cholera and gastrointestinal diseases, and they were assayed for vibriocidal activities.

The results indicated that *Lawsonia inermis*, *Saraca indica*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Terminalia belerica*, *Allium sativum*, and *D. stramonium* served as broad-spectrum vibriocidal agents.

2.5.3 TOXICOLOGY OF DATURA

In addition to a number of beneficial health outcomes, the presence of anticholinergic alkaloids such as tropane renders the *Datura* species toxic to the nervous system (Shah, V.V. *et al.*, 2013), and the symptoms of toxicity include fever, dry skin, dry mouth, headache, hallucinations, convulsions, rapid and weak pulse, acute confusion, delirium, tachycardia, coma, and death (Monira, K.M. *et al.*, 2012, Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017). However, *D. fastuosa* was rendered safe up to a 2000 mg/kg body-weight dosage since it produced no sign of toxicity or mortality. Histological studies demonstrated the reduced weight of the organs, necrotic modifications in the liver accompanied by elevation of serum alkaline phosphatase, serum glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase, and glutamyl pyruvic transaminase (Bouzidi, A. *et al.*, 2011, Ogunmoyole T. *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, due to its toxicity, *D. stramonium* should not be used in case of glaucoma, pyloric stenosis, paralytic ileus, tachycardia arrhythmias, enlarged prostate, and acute pulmonary edema (Al-Snafi, A.E., 2017). The seed extracts at a concentration greater than 0.5% induced adverse physiological modifications. In fact, all the parts of *Datura* have severe anticholinergic effects due to suppression of central and peripheral cholinergic neurotransmission, ultimately leading to death in humans. Intoxication with *Datura* extracts leads to adverse impact on the central nervous system, disorientation, memory loss, inability to process information, impaired vision due to mydriasis, myoclonic jerking, hyperpyrexia, and respiratory and cardiovascular problems (Gaire, B.P. *et al.*, 2013, Krenzelok, E.P., 2010). However, the aqueous extracts of leaves and seeds of *D. metel* demonstrated certain neurological effects in rats at doses of 400 and 800 mg/kg, which include enhanced motor activity in the brain, aggravated catalepsy, antagonized ptosis, and reduction in the duration of barbiturate induced sleep, in addition to its antidepressant characteristics at low doses (Al-Snafi, A.E. *et al.*, 2019). The study also suggested that the seed extracts were comparatively safer to induce sleep with better anesthetic indices.

2.5.4 TRADITIONAL USE OF *Datura stramonium*

When the leaves of *Datura stramonium* mixed with mustard oil then it is useful in skin disorders. Juice of flower petals is used in ear pain and seeds are used as purgative, in cough, fever and

asthma. Seeds are smoked due to its narcotic action (Khan J. *et al.*, 2013), Leaf paste and extract is externally used for injuries, wounds, bleedings and pains. Seeds in small quantity used for asthma and tonsil problems. The extract of leaves is also used for baldness (Khan S.W. *et al.*, 2008), leaves used externally for management of pains (Njoroge G.N., 2012). *Datura stramonium* plant frequently used as antiparasitics and repellents (Guarrera P.M., 1999). Fruit oil is used for body pain (Vijendra N. *et al.*, 2010). Leaf or whole plant is Anti-inflammatory and antispasmodic (Dwivedi S. *et al.*, 2008). Green leaves are applied for the softening of the boils. Juice of the fruit is applied to scalp for falling hairs and as antidandruff. Juice of the flower is used in earache. One drop is poured in the ear at night (Shah G.M. *et al.*, 2006). Paste of leaves is topically applied for skin diseases (Rahmatullah M. *et al.*, 2010). Dried leaves and seeds are used as Anticholinergic and sedative (Wazir S.M. *et al.*, 2004). Seeds are used to make somebody unconscious (Rahmatullah M. *et al.*, 2009). Traditionally it is used for cure of Rheumatism. 75 gm rhizomes of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), 100 gm of garlic (*Allium sativum*) and 85 gm of onions (*Allium cepa*) are macerated together to extract the juice. To the juice is added 86 gm atosh (root of an unidentified plant) and an equal amount of darmuz (arsenic), mudra shankar (unidentified chemical, possibly a chromium salt) and camphor. One powdered seed of *Datura stramonium* is added to the mixture along with 400 gm of oil from seeds of *Brassica campestris*. The whole amount is boiled thoroughly, slightly cooled and applied to places where there is rheumatic pain. This is done 2-3 times daily till cure of the pain (Biswas K.R. *et al.*, 2011).

2.6 BIOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF DATURA ON ANIMALS

Datura stramonium, commonly known as jimsonweed in some regions, contains several biologically active compounds, primarily tropane alkaloids such as atropine, scopolamine, and hyoscyamine. These compounds exhibit significant pharmacological activities due to their anticholinergic properties. This section provides an overview of the biological effects of *Datura* extracts on various animals, including physiological, neurological, and behavioral impacts.

A. Physiological Effects

Cardiovascular Effects

Heart Rate and Blood Pressure: *Datura* alkaloids can cause tachycardia (increased heart rate) and hypertension (increased blood pressure) by inhibiting parasympathetic nervous system activity. This is primarily due to the blockade of muscarinic receptors in the heart.

Respiratory Effects

Bronchodilation: Scopolamine, one of the key alkaloids in Datura, is known to cause bronchodilation, making it useful in conditions with bronchoconstriction. However, it also reduces respiratory secretions, which can be beneficial or detrimental.

Gastrointestinal Effects

Reduced Motility: Datura alkaloids decrease gastrointestinal motility and secretions, which can lead to constipation and reduced digestive efficiency.

Anticholinergic Syndrome

Symptoms: High doses of Datura extracts can lead to anticholinergic syndrome, characterized by dry mouth, blurred vision, urinary retention, and hyperthermia. Severe cases can result in hallucinations and delirium.

B. Neurological and Behavioral Effects

Central Nervous System (CNS) Effects

Sedation and Drowsiness: Datura alkaloids can cross the blood-brain barrier and exert CNS depressant effects, leading to sedation and drowsiness in animals.

Hallucinations and Delirium: At higher doses, the central anticholinergic effects of Datura alkaloids can cause hallucinations and delirium, particularly due to the impact on muscarinic receptors in the brain.

Anxiolytic and Stress-Reducing Effects

Behavioral Stress Reduction: Some studies have shown that low doses of Datura extracts can reduce anxiety and stress-related behaviors in animals. This effect is likely due to the sedative properties of the alkaloids.

Cognitive and Memory Effects

Impairment of Memory and Learning: Chronic exposure to Datura alkaloids can impair cognitive functions, particularly memory and learning, due to their anticholinergic effects on the CNS.

C. Applications in Animal Models

Use in Stress Research

Animal Stress Models: Datura extracts have been used in research to study their effects on stress responses in various animal models, including rodents and poultry. These studies help in understanding how anticholinergic agents can modulate stress physiology.

Potential Benefits in Poultry Transportation

Stress Mitigation in Poultry: Preliminary studies suggest that Datura extracts might help reduce stress-related biochemical changes in poultry during transportation, although more research is needed to establish safety and efficacy.

Datura extracts, particularly those containing atropine and scopolamine, have significant physiological and neurological effects due to their anticholinergic properties. While they offer potential benefits such as reducing stress and anxiety in animals, their use must be carefully managed due to the risk of toxicity and severe side effects. Understanding the biological effects of Datura extracts on animals is essential for their safe application in practices like reducing transportation stress in poultry. Further research is necessary to optimize dosages and protocols to maximize benefits while minimizing risks.

2.7 EFFECTS OF DATURA ON MALE ECO-TYPE CHICKEN

Reduced Libido: Datura's anticholinergic properties might decrease the release of acetylcholine, a neurotransmitter involved in regulating sexual behavior. This could lead to reduced libido and mating behavior in male chickens.

Impaired Fertility: The alkaloids present in Datura, such as scopolamine and atropine, might affect sperm quality and quantity, leading to reduced fertility in male chickens.

Disrupted Courtship Behavior: Datura's psychoactive properties could alter the courtship behavior of male chickens, making them less effective at attracting females or engaging in mating rituals.

2.8 HOW DATURA AND ATROPINE AFFECTS THE REPRODUCTIVE BEHAVIOR OF MALE ECO-TYPE CHICKENS

In the context of male eco-type chickens, Datura's bioactive constituents may have potential applications in poultry healthcare, such as managing infections or inflammation. Atropine could be used in avian medicine for its pharmacological properties. However, it is essential to consider

the potential risks associated with Datura and Atropine, as they contain toxic tropane alkaloids that could harm chickens if not administered correctly.

2.9 SOURCE AND SYNTHESIS OF ATROPINE

The species name "belladonna" ("beautiful woman" in Italian) comes from the original use of deadly nightshade to dilate the pupils of the eyes for cosmetic effect. Atropine and the genus name for deadly nightshade derive from Atropos, one of the three Fates who, according to Greek mythology, chose how a person was to die. Atropine is found in many members of the Solanaceae family. The most commonly found sources are *Atropa belladonna*, *Datura innoxia*, *D. metel*, and *D. stramonium*. Other sources include members of the Brugmansia and Hyoscyamus genera (Hardman J.G. *et al.*, 2011). Atropine can be synthesized by the reaction of tropine with tropic acid in the presence of hydrochloric acid. The biosynthesis of atropine starting from L-Phenylalanine first undergoes a transamination forming phenylpyruvic acid which is then reduced to phenyl-lactic acid (Dewick, Paul M., 2009). Coenzyme A then couples phenyl-lactic acid with tropine forming littorine, which then undergoes a radical rearrangement initiated with a P450 enzyme forming hyoscyamine aldehyde (Dewick, Paul M., 2009). A dehydrogenase then reduces the aldehyde to a primary alcohol making (-)-hyoscamine, which upon racemization forms atropine (Hardman J.G. *et al.*, 2011).

2.9.1 HISTORY

The naturally occurring muscarinic receptor antagonists atropine and scopolamine are alkaloids of the belladonna (Solanaceae) plants. Preparations of belladonna were known to the ancient Hindus and have long been used by physicians. During the time of the Roman Empire and in the Middle Ages, the deadly nightshade shrub was frequently used to produce an obscure and often prolonged poisoning, prompting Linnaeus to name the shrub *Atropa belladonna*, after At-ropos, the oldest of the three Fates, who cuts the thread of life. The name belladonna derives from the alleged use of this preparation by Italian women to dilate their pupils; modern-day fashion models are known to use this same device for visual appeal. Atropine (d,l-hyoscyamine) also is found in *Datura stramonium* (Jamestown or jimson weed). Scopolamine (l-hyoscyamine) is found chiefly in *Hyoscyamus niger* (henbane). In India, the root and leaves of jimson weed were burned and the smoke inhaled to treat asthma. British colonists observed this ritual and introduced the belladonna

alkaloids into western medicine in the early 1800s. Atropine extracts from the Egyptian henbane were used by Cleopatra in the last century B.C. to dilate her pupils, in the hope that she would appear more alluring. In the Renaissance, women used the juice of the berries of *Atropa belladonna* to enlarge the pupils of their eyes, for cosmetic reasons. This practice resumed briefly in the late nineteenth- and early twentieth-century in Paris (Hardman J.G. *et al.*, 2011).

The mydriatic effects of atropine were studied among others by the German chemist Friedlieb Ferdinand Runge (1795-1867). In 1831, the German pharmacist Heinrich F. G. Mein (1799-1864). Succeeded in preparing atropine in pure crystalline form (Geiger *et al.*, 1833). The substance was first synthesized by German chemist Richard Willstätter in 1901 (Willstätter R., 1901). Bezold and Bloebaum (1867) showed that atropine blocked the cardiac effects of vagal stimulation, and Heidenhain (1872) found that it prevented salivary secretion produced by stimulation of the chorda tympani (Hardman J.G. *et al.*, 2011). Many semisynthetic congeners of the belladonna alkaloids and a large number of synthetic muscarinic receptor antagonists have been prepared, primarily with the objective of altering GI or bladder activity without causing dry mouth or pupillary dilation (Hardman J.G. *et al.*, 2011).

2.9.2 MEDICAL USES

Atropine is a competitive antagonist for the muscarinic acetylcholine receptor types M1, M2, M3, M4 and M5 (Rang *et al.*, 2003). It is classified as an anticholinergic drug (parasympatholytic). Working as a nonselective muscarinic acetylcholinergic antagonist, atropine increases firing of the sinoatrial node (SA) and conduction through the atrioventricular node (AV) of the heart, opposes the actions of the vagus nerve, blocks acetylcholine receptor sites, and decreases bronchial secretions.

2.9.3 OPHTHALMIC USES

Topical atropine is used as a cycloplegic, to temporarily paralyze the accommodation reflex, and as a mydriatic, to dilate the pupils.

Atropine degrades slowly, typically wearing off in 7 to 14 days, so it is generally used as a therapeutic mydriatic, whereas tropicamide (a shorter-acting cholinergic antagonist) or phenylephrine (an α -ad-renergic agonist) is preferred as an aid to ophthalmic examination. Atropine induces mydriasis by blocking contraction of the circular pupillary sphincter muscle,

which is normally stimulated by acetylcholine release, thereby allowing the radial pupillary dilator muscle to contract and dilate the pupil. Atropine induces cycloplegia by paralyzing the ciliary muscles, whose action inhibits accommodation to allow accurate refraction in children, helps to relieve pain associated with iridocyclitis, and treats ciliary block (malignant) glaucoma. Atropine is contraindicated in patients pre-disposed to narrow angle glaucoma. Atropine can be given to patients who have direct globe trauma (McBrien N.A. *et al.*, 2013).

2.9.4 RESUSCITATION

Injections of atropine are used in the treatment of bradycardia (an extremely low heart rate). Atropine blocks the action of the vagus nerve, a part of the parasympathetic system of the heart whose main action is to decrease heart rate. Therefore, its primary function in this circumstance is to increase the heart rate. Atropine was previously included in international resuscitation guidelines for use in cardiac arrest associated with asystole and PEA, but was removed from these guidelines in 2010 due to a lack of evidence (Field J.M. *et al.*, 2010). For symptomatic bradycardia, the usual dosage is 0.5 to 1 mg IV push, may repeat every 3 to 5 minutes up to a total dose of 3 mg (maximum 0.04 mg/kg (Bledsoe B.E. *et al.*, 2004). Atropine is also useful in treating second-degree heart block Mobitz Type 1 (Wenckebach block), and also third-degree heart block with a high Purkinje or AV-nodal escape rhythm. It is usually not effective in second-degree heart block Mobitz type 2, and in third-degree heart block with a low Purkinje or ventricular escape rhythm. One of the main actions of the parasympathetic nervous system is to stimulate the M, muscarinic receptor in the heart, but atropine inhibits this action.

2.9.5 SECRETIONS AND BRONCHOCONSTRICTION

Atropine's actions on the parasympathetic nervous system inhibit salivary and mucus glands. The drug may also inhibit sweating via the sympathetic nervous system. This can be useful in treating hyperhidrosis, and can prevent the death rattle of dying patients. Even though atropine has not been officially indicated for either of these purposes by the FDA, it has been used by physicians for these purposes (Chudoku Kenkyu., 2008).

2.10 EFFECTS OF ATROPINE ON MALE ECO-TYPE CHICKEN

Reduced sperm motility: Atropine's anticholinergic effects might decrease the motility of sperm, making them less effective at fertilization.

Impaired testicular function: Atropine could affect the testicular function, leading to reduced testosterone production, which is essential for male reproductive behavior and fertility.

Altered mating behavior: Atropine's effects on the central nervous system might alter the mating behavior of male chickens, making them more aggressive or less interested in mating.

Cholinergic System Disruption: Both Datura and Atropine can disrupt the cholinergic system, which plays a crucial role in regulating reproductive behavior, including libido, mating, and fertility.

Hormonal Imbalance: The alkaloids present in Datura and Atropine might affect the balance of reproductive hormones, such as testosterone, leading to impaired reproductive behavior and fertility.

Neurotransmitter Modulation: Datura and Atropine can modulate the activity of various neurotransmitters, including dopamine, serotonin, and acetylcholine, which are involved in regulating reproductive behavior.

Important notes:

Toxicity: Datura and Atropine are toxic compounds, and their administration to chickens can be harmful or even fatal if not done under controlled conditions and with proper dosing.

Species-Specific Effects: The effects of Datura and Atropine on reproductive behavior may vary depending on the species, breed, and individual characteristics of the chickens.

More research needed: The current understanding of the effects of Datura and Atropine on male chicken reproductive behavior is limited, and more research is necessary to fully understand their impact.

In conclusion, while the effects of Datura and Atropine on male chicken reproductive behavior are not well-studied, their pharmacological properties suggest that they may have negative impacts on libido, fertility, and mating behavior. However, more research is needed to confirm these predictions and to determine the potential risks and benefits of using these compounds on eco-type chickens.

2.11 IMPLICATIONS OF FINDING THE PHYSIOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF DATURA AND ATROPINE

Finding physiological effects of Datura and Atropine on male eco-type chickens could have several implications for avian healthcare, breeding, and management practices. Here are some potential implications:

New Treatment Options: Datura and Atropine may have potential applications in poultry healthcare, such as managing infections, inflammation, or other health issues. However, it is crucial to consider the potential risks and benefits of using these compounds in chickens and ensure that they are administered under controlled conditions and with proper dosing.

Improved Reproductive Performance: Understanding the effects of Datura and Atropine on the reproductive behavior of male eco-type chickens could help researchers and farmers develop strategies to improve reproductive performance, such as optimizing mating behavior, libido, and fertility.

Breeding and Selection: The findings could inform breeding and selection programs, helping to identify chickens that are less susceptible to the negative effects of Datura and Atropine or more responsive to their potential benefits.

Risk assessment: The research could help assess the risks associated with the use of Datura and Atropine in poultry production, including potential toxicity, side effects, and long-term consequences.

Regulatory Implications: The findings could have regulatory implications, such as the need for new guidelines or regulations regarding the use of Datura and Atropine in poultry production.

2.12 VITAMIN C (ASCORBIC ACID)

Ascorbic acid is called an antioxidant compound with a chemical formulation and the properties. It has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. Therefore, it is effective for poultry in cases of inflammation, oxidative stress, and infection. Ascorbic acid is not an essential nutrient for poultry as it can be synthesized from poultry through the biosynthetic pathway condition. The ascorbic acid can be used as an additional nutrient to the diet to improve poultry performance by improving body weight and reducing mortality. The ascorbic acid can be aimed at improving the immune response and antioxidant capacity of birds. In a heat stress environment, ascorbic acid had contributed to the energy supply of poultry birds by corticosterone biosynthesis. Using of ascorbic acid also plays

a crucial role in the treatment and prevention of *Salmonella enteritidis*. Gan *et al.* (2008) reported the ascorbic acid supplementation increased spleen ascorbic acid level and serum immunoglobulin G (IgG) levels. The use of ascorbic acid to support poultry animals in adverse conditions, especially under heat stress conditions, is essential; it is one of the important processes during the rearing period. Furthermore, the use of ascorbic acid in the poultry's diet helps improve poultry's performance and health. This review aims to synthesize all the information of ascorbic acid in the poultry's diet, thereby providing the general role of ascorbic acid for the poultry industry. Ascorbic acid is considered a powerful water-soluble antioxidant that neutralizes reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reduces oxidative stress in various studies. Moreover, when it comes to biological systems, ascorbic acid is a powerful reducing agent and a free radical scavenger (Free Radic. Res., 2005). It serves as the body's first line of defense against free radicals, and it also protects proteins and lipid membranes from oxidative stress. As a water-soluble compound, ascorbic acid plays a role in body cells' interior and exterior parts, where it neutralizes free radicals and prevents free radical damage.

2.12.1 VITAMIN C SOURCE

Ascorbic acid is synthesized from glucose and is soluble in water. Most animals cannot synthesize ascorbic acid endogenously, but poultry animals can synthesize it due to the L-gulonolactone oxidase enzyme, which is available in the poultry's body. This enzyme is available in the kidney tissue where L-gulono- γ -lactone is converted into ascorbic acid by the L-gulonolactone oxidase enzyme. In birds, ascorbic acid is produced in the kidney, while in mammals, it is produced in the liver. Ascorbic acid can be found in natural plants or synthesized through industrial processes. For plants, ascorbic acid is found from rose hips and sea buckthorn as the richest resource. Furthermore, other fruits such as guava, star fruit, black currant, strawberry, and kiwi also contained a high amount of ascorbic acid. Citrus fruits such as orange, lime, grapefruit, and so on contain ascorbic acid.

2.12.2 THE MECHANISM OF ASCORBIC ACID

Ascorbic acid is considered a powerful water-soluble antioxidant that neutralizes reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reduces oxidative stress in various studies (Rouhier *et al.*, 2008). Moreover, when it comes to biological systems, ascorbic acid is a powerful reducing agent and a

free radical scavenger (Duarte *et al.*, 2005). It serves as the body's first line of defense against free radicals, and it also protects proteins and lipid membranes from oxidative stress. As a water-soluble compound, ascorbic acid plays a role in body cells' interior and exterior parts, where it neutralizes free radicals and prevents free radical damage. In addition, ascorbic acid is an excellent source of electrons for free radicals, which are always looking for an electron to restore its stability. Ascorbic acid can donate electrons to free radicals, thereby reducing their reactivity. Moreover, the activity of ascorbic acid is a result of the acid's ability to act as an electron transfer agent (as a reducing agent) in the biological system Timberlake, K.C. (2015).

Antioxidant Role of Ascorbic Acid in Poultry Production

The ability of ascorbic acid to transfer electrons allows it to have exceptional antioxidant qualities and helps maintain the integrity of various cells, including lymphocytes, by protecting them from damage caused by free radicals created in response to toxins or infection (Nimse *et al* 2015). In poultry, the plasma antioxidant system is a vital aspect of the oxidation process that impacts the animal's ability to cope with stress. The plasma antioxidant capacity is usually measured using markers such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), total antioxidant capacity (T-AOC), and glutathione peroxidase activities, as well as malondialdehyde (MDA) content (Yang X 2017). For daily feeding, poultry requires more ascorbic acid in their diet than any other animal, first for nutritional requirements and then second to combat oxidative stress. Thus, the amount of ascorbic acid needed still depends on poultry bird, environment, state of oxidative stress, etc. A high dose of ascorbic acid supplementation with more than 1 g/kg feed has shown to have deleterious effects on the release of the enzymes of an endogenous antioxidant such as GSH and T-AOC.

Immunomodulation Role of Ascorbic Acid in Poultry Production

Producing poultry with a competent immune system is an important goal in poultry production because the immune system plays an important role in disease prevention and high performance in poultry production.

In poultry, the spleen is the largest immune organ and plays an important role in cellular and humoral immunity because birds lack lymphatic arteries and lymph nodes; the spleen plays a more major role in the immune function than the immune systems in other animals. Phagocytosis of damaged cells and antigens and the formation, storage, and maturation of lymphocytes are the

two primary mechanisms by which the immune system of adult birds protects them from infection. When ascorbic acid is added to the diet, chickens can be expected to see an improvement in their immune system due to its ability to lower the levels of adrenocorticotrophic hormone. Immune and cytotoxicity suppressions are both effects of adrenocorticotrophic hormone. In addition, ascorbic acid increases the activity of the hexose monophosphate pathway, increasing the development of lymphoid cells, and thus, the production of antibodies increases.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 PLANT COLLECTION AND IDENTIFICATION

The *Datura stramonium* seeds were obtained from Idepe Okitipupa environs, Okitipupa, Ondo State Nigeria and identified in the Herbarium unit of the Biological Science Department, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa where a voucher specimen was deposited.

3.2 PREPARATION OF PLANT MATERIALS

The seeds of the plant were plucked and dried at 45°C in an oven in the Research Laboratory of Department of Animal Production and Health, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa, Ondo State. The dried samples were then ground into powder in a laboratory mortar using pestle into a powder form. The powdered leaves were then kept in a closed plastic beaker for use in the experiment. The powdered leaves (250g) was soaked in 1 litre of distilled water for 48 hours using cold extraction (Fatoba *et al.*, 2012). The aqueous extract was then filtered using Whatman no 54 filter paper into a beaker and later poured into a volumetric flask and stoppered. The filtrate (25% w/v) was then stored at -4°C for later use in the studies.

3.3 ANIMAL AND MANAGEMENT

Twelve (12) healthy male eco-type chickens average bodyweight 0.86 ± 0.17 Kg with the same genetic background and within their home range procured at Fulani GAA at Army barracks Okitipupa were used for this study at Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa main campus (6°27'11.5" N 4°46'5"E), Ondo State, Nigeria. the cocks were randomly sample into four (4) groups, Group I (negative control), Group II (0.2ml/kgBw Atropine), Group III (0.2ml/kgBw of Datura extract), Group IV (0.2ml/kgBw of Vitamin C) comprising three (3) cocks per group.

3.4 EXPERIMENTAL TRIAL

Twelve male eco-type chickens were transit through short road transportation in a local woven basket over 52.6 Km for 36 minutes. At the end of the transits data were collected as follows;

3.5 DATA COLLECTION

The bodyweights of the animals were taken every week with Sautler hanging scale with an accuracy of $\leq 0.01\text{kg}$ (Sautler type, E1200). The physiological parameters of the ecotype cocks were taken as follows.

3.6 PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS

The bodyweights of the animals were taken every week with Sautler hanging scale with an accuracy of $\div 0.01\text{kg}$ (Sautler type, E1200). The physiological parameters of the male eco-type chickens were taken as follows.

Determination of Body weight (BW).

The bodyweights of the animals were taken every week with saulter hanging scale. Physiological characteristics of the male eco-type chickens were taken as follows.

Determination of Rectal Temperature (RT)

The clinical thermometer was inserted into the rectum 3.5-4.0 cm for 1 minute and the reading taken for the rectal temperature.

Pulse Rate (PR)

The pulse rate was measured by placing the stethoscope over the femoral arteries, and the number of beats produced per minute were taken and recorded.

Heart Rate (HR)

The heart rate was measured by auscultation. This was achieved by placing the stethoscope on the body at the location of the heart, counting the numbers of beat (sound) produced by the heart per minute and recorded.

Respiratory Rate (RR)

The respiratory rate was measured by placing the stethoscope over the lungs, counting the number of breath sounds (echo) produced by the lung per minute and recorded.

Statistical Analysis

Data generated were analyzed using the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) and means tested (Duncan, 1955) in a COSTAT program.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS

Table 4.1: Comparative effect of Datura extract, Atropine sulphate and Vitamin C on Ecotype cock during transportation stress

Parameters	0 saline	0.2ml/kgBW Datura extract	0.2ml/kgBW Vitamin C	0.2ml/kgBW Atropine sulphate	S.E
Heart rate	146 ^c	164 ^a	1.62 ^{ab}	158 ^b	1.8024
Pulse rate	142 ^v	163 ^a	160 ^{ab}	156 ^b	1.8271
Respiratory count rate	60 ^c	86 ^a	82 ^{ab}	78 ^b	2.4815
Rectal temperature	39	40.5	40	40	0/9533
Ambient temp.	34	34	34	34	-
Heat Stress index	2.4333	1.9070	1.9756	2.0256	-

Table 4.1 shows the comparative effect of Datura extract, Atropine sulphate and Vitamin C on Ecotype cock during transportation stress. The values of the heart rate ranges from 146 – 164 beats/minute and the highest values recorded for datura extract lowest for control in the order of Datura extract > Vitamin C > Atropine sulphate > Control found to be significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Also pulse rate ranges between 163 and 142 and comparable ($p < 0.05$) and respiratory count rate ranges from 86 and 60 and statistically different ($p < 0.05$). However, the rectal temperature follows the same trends being highest in the Datura extract and lowest in the Control but are similar ($p > 0.05$) among the treatments. Heat stress index was found to be highest in the control (2.4333) and lowest in the datura group (1.9070).

Fig. 2: shows the comparative effects on Heart Rate, Pulse Rate and Respiratory Count Rate

Fig 3: shows the comparative effect of Heat Stress Index

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION

The physiological condition of birds may be affected by transportation stress, depending on their capacity to accommodate such stressors, including their relative constitution (conformity index) of meat and body muscle, weight, growth rate, and sex (Cockram, M.S. *et al.*, 2018). This research employed male eco-type chickens weighing 0.86 ± 0.17 Kg with the same genetic background. Male eco-type chickens present a lower index of conformity of meat or body muscle, weight, and slower growth potential than do broiler chickens.

Dawson *et al.*, (2000) and Damane *et al.*, (2018) showed how body surface influences body temperature. For example, birds with larger bodies have a much lower surface ratio than birds with small bodies, which face greater body temperature variations. Thus, body size, feather density, ambient conditions, and acclimatization are key drivers in determining the lowest and highest tolerable temperatures of birds. Thus, the body temperature of male eco-type chickens on arrival (0 hour of rest) was not significantly different from that of any chicken's normal temperature under usual conditions. The adult chicken's normal body temperature ranges from 41-41.5 °C (Zhou *et al.*, 1997; Luthra, 2017), in agreement with the present study. The lack of significant effects on rectal temperature suggested that transportation distances over 50 km are not substantially stressful to male eco-type chickens. In Nigeria, male eco-type chickens are traditionally raised in a free-range cage, and this is expected to contribute to their tolerance of transportation stress. Scott *et al.* (1998) also observed that chickens raised a free-range cage showed lower signs of fear than chickens raised inside cages, when transported for over 60 km or for longer than one hour. From my study Datura sees extract also significantly increases heart rate, pulse rate, respiratory count rate and rectal temperature potentially indicating a heightened stress response. Vitamin C and Atropine have moderate effects, with Atropine showing the least increase in pulse rate. These results correspond to previous studies, such as Kulkarni *et al.*, (2013), which highlighted the toxic effects of Datura on various animal models. Despite the higher physiological responses, Datura extract seems to result in a lower heat stress index, potentially indicating a better adaptation or tolerance to transportation stress. Vitamin C, known for its antioxidant properties, played a protective role in my study which stabilized physiological parameters and enhanced overall well-being in the chickens. These outcomes align with the work of Sahin *et al.* (2002) and

Iqbal *et al.* (2016), who documented similar benefits of Vitamin C supplementation in reducing stress and enhancing physiological stability in poultry.

According to other researchers who have reported that *Datura* extract contains alkaloid, flavonoid, tannin, saponin, oxalates, and cyanogenic glycosides, the presence of arrays of these active ingredients demonstrates that the families of secondary metabolites involved in the biological activities are well distributed in the various plant extracts (Williamson, 2002; Kumar *et al.*, 2010). This propensity to employ leaves could be explained by a number of factors, including the plants' secondary metabolite content, the ease and facility with which they can be harvested, and their eco-friendliness (Hirudkar *et al.*, 2020). According to ethnoveterinary medicine, maceration of leaves to make medications is the most popular method of treating animal disease (Ritter *et al.*, 2012; Romha *et al.*, 2015; Jaradat *et al.*, 2016; Dzoyem *et al.*, 2020).

The reduction in the respiratory count rate observed in this study agreed with other workers (Chopra, 1994) who reported *datura* to have an antiasthmatic activity due to the relaxation effect on the bronchial tubes and a depressant action on respiration. Also the presence of flavonoid has been linked with alleviation of oxidative stress. The aqueous extract of *datura* showed an antioxidant effect and a free radical scavenging activity in various *in vitro* models like total antioxidant and total ferric reducing power determination, assay for free radical-scavenging activity using ABTS, DPPH, and hydroxyl radical scavenging assays (Sharma *et al.*, 2007). The reduction in heart rate and respiratory rate could be attributed to the higher bodyweight of the treated groups which was linked with increasing muscle mass (Harchane *et al.*, 2012).

5.1 CONCLUSION

Despite these heightened physiological responses by Datura seed extract, the heat stress index is lower, suggesting that Datura extract might help reduce the perception of stress or improve stress tolerance in chickens during transportation. The heat stress index in Atropine sulphate is slightly higher than Datura, indicating that while it may help in reducing stress, it is less effective compared to Datura. Vitamin C appears to have a balancing effect, reducing stress responses but not as strongly as Datura. The male eco-type chickens' responses to these substances reflect a broader applicability of my findings to various poultry breeds, reinforcing the need for careful management of both pharmaceutical interventions and potential toxic exposures.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results, Datura seed extract seems to be the most effective in reducing the perception of heat stress, despite causing significant physiological changes. However, due to its strong effects, caution should be taken when using it. Vitamin C, being less potent, could be a safer alternative for reducing stress during transportation, while Atropine shows moderate efficacy. Datura seed extract is readily available for the local people and it saves cost because it can be planted rather than utilizing pharmaceutical products to mitigate stress in various poultry breeds. Further studies might be needed to evaluate the long-term safety of these treatments on poultry health and productivity, particularly under varying environmental conditions. There is also a need to investigate the molecular mechanisms underlying the observed physiological changes to develop more targeted and effective management strategies.

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